

Using Information Theory to More Fully Exploit the Electromagnetic Spectrum: Lessons for Regulators

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Abstract—This paper takes tools arising from information theory, used to analyze modulation and coding trade-offs in digital system design, and extends them to the regulation of the electromagnetic spectrum. The benefits to existing spectrum users under the regulatory regime of technical flexibility are demonstrated in the use of the bandwidth-efficiency plane, which shows that extra communications capabilities can be created without sacrificing competitive system performance, if extra communications resources of power or bandwidth are available. Other regulatory policies that encourage spectrum leasing and facilitate secondary markets would permit licensees to take these extra communications capabilities more directly to the marketplace. In addition, it is demonstrated that the imposition of a requirement external to the goals of system design—*e.g.*, operating at a noise level other than that of the original design—would appear to be a “tax” on either the performance of the system or the communications resources themselves. Regulatory decisions have been made that permit increased licensed and unlicensed access based on findings that, while such a “tax” exists for particular circumstances, it is minimal and its impact, “acceptable.”

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Introductory Note

While theories of economics and law, treating private versus communal property rights and other issues, have properly been used to analyze alternative approaches to regulating access to the electromagnetic spectrum, one highly important area of knowledge, which one may say is absolutely fundamental to spectrum use, appears not to have been used at all in the discussion of technically and economically efficient use of the resource—information theory. This paper seeks to open a discussion of the subject by using information *theory* to illustrate regulatory *practice*. This paper does not address any of the issues surrounding property rights, communal access, and other approaches and takes no position on these matters. There is no opinion as to what the Federal Communications Commission “should” or “should not” do. Principles of information theory that govern signal bandwidth and power are related to the spectrum user’s technical and business performance goals and used to illustrate the consumption of communications resources and the impact of regulatory actions.

B. Design of Digital Communications Systems

The design of a digital communications system involves a set of decisions on the part of the circuit designer. These decisions involve objectives typically concerning how much data is to be transmitted per second and limits on the probability that some bits may be received in error. The two fundamental communications resources available for the design, bandwidth and power, are to be expended most economically in order to achieve system design objectives most efficiently.¹ Reference [1] sets out the design problem and identifies the goals and trade-offs.

A number of factors must be considered in the design, and a key factor is the noise environment within which the stream of bits must be detected. In addition other factors are involved such as vulnerability to interference and system complexity and cost. The designs are ultimately implemented considering the physical aspects of the system—whether the transmitters and receivers are fixed or moving, or perhaps located in a satellite that could be in either a geostationary or non-geostationary orbit. The actual design involves the recognition on the part of the designer that there are inherent conflicts—and hence trade-offs—among these factors, *e.g.*, maximizing the number of correct bits-per-second through a channel is not consistent with minimizing expenditures of bandwidth and power.

C. Limitations Set by the FCC and by Information Theory

Important to this paper are two sets of limitations within which these design trade-offs must be made. The first set deals with the fact that the expenditures of bandwidth and power in the system design are made consistent with the FCC regulations governing the size of the block of spectrum available under the license and the limits on radiated power. Even in a regime of technical flexibility, where the designer has significant freedom, FCC

* The views expressed in this paper are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of Federal Communications Commission.
¹ Bernard Sklar, *Digital Communications*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey 07458, second edition, 2001, p. 521.

regulations on bandwidth and power must be observed.² The second set deals with theoretical and practical limitations from information theory, which is the discipline that deals with the quantification and analysis of information and that reveals the relationships among the rate and the reliability of information in terms of the power and bandwidth of the information signal and the noise of the environment.

Schemes for processing information from its source, through the channel and ultimately to its destination involve coding and modulation and are important to the optimum performance of communications systems. The fundamental theorem of information theory is the Shannon-Hartley Theorem, which gives the relationship between the maximum data rate, called the “channel capacity,” that can be achieved in a channel disturbed with additive white Gaussian noise as a function of the average signal power and the signal bandwidth [2]. Any data rate less than this maximum rate can be achieved in practice with arbitrarily small error rates, if the coding scheme is sufficiently complex. Data rates exceeding the channel capacity are not practical and would lead to systems with large error probabilities. A graph showing channel capacity as a boundary between practical and impractical systems will be used later in this paper to illustrate alternative coding schemes and the performance of practical systems. The capacity theorem is very general and not restricted to Gaussian channels.

The designer of a communications system usually considers trade-offs between two key parameters, signal power (or in the case of digital signals, energy-per-bit) and the bandwidth. A customary optimum design could have as a goal a specified desired level of throughput of information at a minimum probability of error that would be accomplished with a minimum expenditure of the limited communications resources available.

The fundamental contribution of this paper is to present an extension of the heuristic model for the design of digital communications systems, where design trade-offs are considered under FCC regulatory constraints, to a model for the analysis and demonstration of regulatory policies under the fundamental constraints of information theory.

D. Roadmap of Paper

In the following discussion, a customary design is described, with explicit definitions of the parameters governing the digital system design: desired goals, communications resources, and constraints. Important

measures of resource utilization or efficiency will be defined: bandwidth efficiency and power (or energy) efficiency. The customary design is illustrated as selecting an operating point in a region representing practical systems. Different designs appear as different operating points in the vicinity of the design operating points.

Next, designs that are alternative to the customary system design are illustrated in which the possible availability of unused communications resources of bandwidth and power are exploited to develop extra communications capabilities, beyond the desired design goals. Such illustrations are shown in regions in the vicinity of the original operating point.

Lastly, using these methods, this paper demonstrates how the design and the performance of a digital communications system are affected by the imposition of a requirement external to the goals of the system design, *e.g.*, operating at a noise level higher than that of the original design. The impact is illustrated as a “tax” on either the performance of the system or on the communications resources. It is not the intent of this paper to argue whether such a “tax” is justifiable, merely that it exists.

II. TOOLS FROM INFORMATION THEORY

A. Model for Digital System Design

From the perspective of commercial communications and a licensee’s capability and strategy to deliver a certain quality of service to the marketplace, the designer of a digital communications systems could begin by identifying a desired transmission rate upon which the service would be based and a bit error rate or reliability that would be essential to the nature of the service. These are shown in the table below along with their units. More specifically, the desired data rate would be at least as large as a minimum rate needed for the application and other aspects of the design; and the bit error rate would be no more than a maximum tolerable error rate. Other factors may be considered such as reducing the system complexity and cost.

DESIGN PARAMETERS	SYMBOL	UNITS
Transmission Bit Rate	R	Bits/Second
Bit Error Rate	P _B	Dimensionless

It is entirely reasonable to use a desired reliable data rate as one of the main criteria for the design of digital communications systems. In fact, the FCC uses equivalent data rate in bits-per-second and equivalent thresholds for bit error rate in defining comparable facilities, which is a threshold requirement for relocating to new bands

² Technical flexibility refers to the regulatory policy that permits the licensees the freedom to implement voluntarily chosen standards rather than detailed technical and compatibility standards that have been mandated. The first implementation of technical flexibility was for cell phones in 1988; see FCC Report & Order Gen. Doc. 87-390, at p. 2.

incumbent licensees who are displaced by new service entrants into the band.³

Next, the designer, seeking the best system design for delivering a desired reliable data rate to compete in the market, would work with the communications resources of bandwidth and power associated with alternative circuit designs. These are shown in the table below along with their symbols and units. How much communications resources the designer has to work with is derived from constraints on spectrum and power limited by FCC regulations and terms of spectrum access.

COMMUNICATIONS RESOURCES	SYMBOL	UNITS
Bandwidth	W	Hertz
Power or Energy-Per-Bit	P or E_b	Watts or Watt-Seconds

The environment in which the system is to operate is frequently described as a channel, and in this situation the environment is characterized by the noise power spectral density (PSD). The problem of determining the probability of correctly detecting a bit in the noisy channel as a function of the bit energy and the noise environment is fundamental to the design of digital communications systems.

CHANNEL ENVIRONMENT	SYMBOL	UNITS
Noise Power Spectral Density (PSD)	N_o	Watts/Hertz

Important measures of the performance of the system reflect the use of the communications resources of bandwidth and energy, examined relative to, respectively, the data rate and the noise PSD. These are shown in the table below. It is important to note that these measures contain the two parameters that are directly affected by FCC regulations. They also reflect the designer's goals of data rate and reliability, which is directly derived from the bit-energy efficiency.

MEASURES OF PERFORMANCE & EFFICIENCY	SYMBOL	UNITS
Bandwidth Efficiency	R/W	Bits/Second/Hertz
Bit Energy/ Noise Power Spectral Density	E_b/N_o	Dimension-less

The bandwidth efficiency indicates the amount of data can be communicated in the bandwidth within a certain time. The energy efficiency is used to measure the amount of power needed, given the noise level, to achieve a desired bit

error probability. A third measure of performance, the bit error probability, was introduced above.

The actual design following a customary approach consists of using the communications resources of bandwidth and power to choose a modulation and coding scheme that achieves the desired objectives and involves trade-offs among the various parameters. The desirable direction of the trade-off for each parameter is indicated in the table below. The trade-offs can be viewed as costs or gains of the parameter relative to the desired goal.

PARAMETER	SYMBOL	GOAL
Bit Error Probability	P_b	Minimize
Data Rate	R	Maximize
Bandwidth	W	Minimize
Bit Energy/ Noise PSD	E_b/N_o	Minimize
Noise PSD	N_o	Fixed

B. Bandwidth Efficiency Plane

Pioneering work in [3] and [4] on a structure for examining design trade-offs for digital communications systems appears to date from the early work of B. Sklar and is used in [1] in the analysis of modulation and coding trade-offs. Representations of the trade-offs are usually shown in a pair of graphs called the bandwidth efficiency plane and the error probability plane. System performance is examined with simple examples to show the trade-offs among bit error probability, bandwidth, and power between different modulation and coding schemes.

The particular graph that is used in this paper is the bandwidth efficiency plane and is shown in Figure 1. The Shannon capacity boundary separates the regions of practical, implementable systems from those that are not theoretically possible. This is a graph of the channel data rate normalized to the bandwidth versus the channel E_b/N_o . The bandwidth efficiency plane shows the limiting performance that can be achieved by practical systems represented as a point below the Shannon capacity limit. The axes of the graph are measures of how the communications resources, bandwidth and power (or energy), are consumed to yield certain performance measures, data rate and bit error probability. The bandwidth efficiency plane is useful in comparing the trade-offs for different designs represented by different operating points in the bandwidth efficiency plane in selecting a system design.

A point within the region below the Shannon capacity boundary between practical and impractical systems represents a particular selection of modulation and coding scheme for the system design, e.g., 16-level QAM. The corresponding bandwidth efficiency and energy efficiency on the axes for this system operating point indicate the design levels of R/W and E_b/N_o . Alternative

³ See Microwave Cost Sharing First R&O and FNPRM, 11 F.C.C. Rcd. 8825 at ¶¶ 27-34 (2000). See also 47 C.F.R. §§ 101.73, 101.75, 101.91.

designs for different schemes would consume resources consistent with those alternative modulation/coding schemes and would yield corresponding bit error rates. The principal task of the system designer is to consider the trade-offs among the resources and the compromises among the other parameters of the design, with an eye to the design goals and the constraining factors, and to select the final choice of modulation and coding.

Figure 1. Bandwidth Efficiency Plane: Selecting a Modulation & Coding Scheme

The regulatory policy of technical flexibility can be explained as the freedom afforded the licensee and hence the system designer to pick any point in the plane, *i.e.*, to select any operating point that delivers the desired performance. This is based on two fundamental considerations: designing for the goal of having a system with a desired reliable data rate that would deliver competitive services to the marketplace and expending the least amount of power and bandwidth to achieve that goal. Thus the design is said to be an optimal one. Restrictions on any of the design parameters would be considered limitations on the design flexibility afforded the licensee.

Sklar is careful to point out the heuristic nature of the presentation of trade-offs that use the bandwidth efficiency and the error probability planes along with simple examples.⁴ Although this has proven useful for most modulation and coding schemes, design trade-offs concerning some codes and combined modulation and coding schemes may involve performance curves that do not follow as predictably the simple examples. Indeed, more complex codes developed to achieve specific objectives may yield performance curves that behave differently; BCH codes and trellis-coded modulation are cited. In addition the usual representation of the bandwidth efficiency plane illustrates efficiency trade-offs for single carrier systems.

⁴ B. Sklar, *op. cit.*, p. 538.

For multiple carrier systems, the concepts would have to be expanded.

For the purposes of this paper, the simple, heuristic nature of the bandwidth efficiency plane presentation is adequate to demonstrate the benefits of exploiting more fully communications resources and the problems of imposing external constraints on the design of digital communications systems. It is not the intent here to prove the existence of highly complex coding and modulation schemes to guarantee the performance of highly dynamic communications systems. This paper seeks to use the theory of information and its principles to illustrate the impact of practical regulatory actions on the efficient consumption of resources of bandwidth and power.

III. EXTRA COMMUNICATIONS CAPABILITY, IF EXTRA RESOURCES AVAILABLE

In the preceding section, the customary design of a digital communications was illustrated by the selection of a coding and modulation scheme that achieved the desired reliable data rate, consistent with the expenditures of communications resources of bandwidth and power. This selection is represented by the operating point on the bandwidth-efficiency plane figure. This section goes further and shows that alternative designs may be possible that not only achieve the desired reliable data rate, but also create extra communications capabilities, above and beyond those needed by in the system design. FCC regulatory policies permit the direct exploitation of these extra communications capabilities.

In addition to being useful in examining design trade-offs and in selecting a system to achieve the design objectives, the bandwidth efficiency plane is also useful in demonstrating how the exploitation of possible additional resources of bandwidth and power, if available, could create extra communications capabilities.

Figure 2 shows the bandwidth efficiency plane and specifically shows the design levels for the three parameters bandwidth efficiency R/W , the energy efficiency E_b/N_0 and the resulting bit error probability P_B . The operating point for the original design is shown on a curve of P_B values equal to the design-level P_B . The continuous curve segment shown for the design-level P_B is a hypothetical construction⁵ for arbitrary operating points and modulation and coding schemes. At the intersection of the three lines designating the design-levels for R/W , E_b/N_0 , and P_B , six regions are shown in the immediate vicinity of the original design operating point. (The areas are enlarged for illustrative purposes.)

Alternative operating points in these six regions, in principle, illustrate alternative trade-offs with differing

⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 536.

results. In the regions above the horizontal line for the design-level R/W , the values of R/W would be larger than the design level. A larger value of R/W would be achieved with a smaller system bandwidth W in the denominator, since the data rate R in the numerator is fixed as a design objective; that is, less bandwidth would be consumed for the same desired rate. This could be interpreted as making more bandwidth available from the bandwidth resource. In the regions below the line the opposite condition occurs: a smaller R/W implies more bandwidth would be expended, relative to the original design, for the same data rate.

Figure 2. System Operating Point for Design-Levels of R/W , E_b/N_0 , and P_B

For the other axis of the graph, regions to the right of the vertical line for the design-level E_b/N_0 , the values of E_b/N_0 would be larger. Assuming a fixed noise level N_0 , a larger value of E_b/N_0 implies the additional expenditure of power (or energy). On the other hand, in regions to the left of the vertical line, operating points would have lower levels of E_b/N_0 . The condition to the left of the vertical line could be interpreted in two ways. Lesser values of E_b/N_0 could be achieved by consuming less power (or energy), thereby making more power available from the resource. Another interpretation would be that the design would have an operating point at the same power (or energy) level as the original, but with a higher noise floor level. In other words the operating points to the left of the vertical line could be viewed as modulation and coding schemes with the same consumption of power, but with a higher tolerance to noise. This latter interpretation will be important to the resource trade-offs yielding extra communications capability. Finally, in regions below the curve for the design-level P_B are found operating points for systems with values of P_B that are better relative to the design-level P_B . Above this curve are operating points that have degraded performance for bit error probability relative to the original design.

In each of the six regions in the vicinity of the original operating point, the trade-offs are different and

yield different measures of performance. Figure 3 identifies these six regions with letters for the purpose of distinguishing the situations in these regions. The trade-offs in the regions can be evaluated as costs or gains in the parameters as appropriate to that region.

Before we examine these trade-offs, let us consider the original design from the perspective of the spectrum resources of bandwidth and power. A natural assumption to make is that the final design satisfying the desired objectives consumes the spectrum resources in a relatively complete way, and it is certainly possible that the spectrum resources are completely consumed in the design. However, it is also possible that perhaps some bandwidth or some power might remain after the operating point is selected for the optimum system. This could correspond to situations where an economical design would have power or bandwidth to spare or where power or bandwidth is not at a premium to begin with. If there were a significant amount of both resources remaining after the final design, then the design would not be optimal and could very likely be improved upon. This is consistent with the fact that in many communications systems one of resources of bandwidth or power is more precious than the other. Terms such as bandwidth-limited systems or power-limited systems are used to describe these circumstances. This reality may be taken into consideration when designing digital systems. An interpretation in this paper is that it is possible in many communications systems that some unused spectrum resources are remaining and available, that is, either bandwidth or power maybe available after the optimized original design, but not both. It is possible that no extra resources are left over, and no potential exists to extract more out of the spectrum. (The trade-offs directly between bandwidth and power in bandwidth-limited systems or power-limited systems are familiar ones and can be made in order to preserve the more precious resource, apart from any other design goal.)

Regions A, B, and C in Figure 3 contain operating points of alternative system designs whose performances in terms of bit error probability would be better than the original design. Systems in Region A are not of interest here, since they would require additional resources of both bandwidth and power. A fully optimized design would not have both extra bandwidth and extra power left over after the original design selection.

Systems in Regions B or C, on the other hand, are very much of interest. They illustrate designs in which extra resources if available could be traded for extra communications capabilities and still achieve the original design objectives. To illustrate, in Region B extra power, if available, could be traded for extra bandwidth that is not needed to satisfy the system design goals. (Region B contains operating points with values of R/W that are larger than the design-level R/W and thus would have a smaller W and with values of E_b/N_0 that are larger than the design-level

E_b/N_0 and thus would require more power.) In Region C extra bandwidth, if available, could be traded for extra power or alternatively for a higher tolerance of noise in the original design. (Region C contains operating points with values of R/W that are smaller than the design-level R/W and would thus require more bandwidth W and with values of E_b/N_0 that are smaller than the design-level E_b/N_0 and permit the system to operate at the same power, but at an increased level of N_0 , that is, a system performance more tolerant of noise levels.)

The expenditure of extra, but presumably available, resources in either Region B or Region C would yield alternative system designs that exceeded the desired data rate and bit error probability performance of the original design and at the same time would yield respectively extra bandwidth or tolerance of higher noise levels.

Figure 3. Regions of Alternative Operating Points. Levels of R/W , E_b/N_0 , and P_B and Six Nearby Regions

Extra bandwidth for systems in Region B is directly translatable into a communications resource, the value of which could be determined in an open commercial exchange, while the original performance goals would be maintained or exceeded. Similarly, a higher tolerance of noise in Region C could be translated into the extra capability to permit other systems to operate in the band thereby increasing the noise level, the value of which could be determined in an open commercial exchange, while the original performance goals would be maintained or exceeded. It should be clear that the extra capability would not be obtained for free.

Resources of bandwidth or power would be expended, but the presumption is that these resources were not needed in the original optimal design that consumed the resources most conservatively. If the return on the value of this extra investment in extra communications capabilities

were sufficient for the licensee to choose to implement such alternative schemes with extra communications capabilities, then the spectrum resource would be more intensely used. This is a highly desirable outcome from the perspective of spectrum utilization.

From another perspective operating points in Regions D, E, and F are not of interest in this paper, since they represent operating points that have degraded performance relative to the desired design-level P_B . It is possible that the licensee might choose to compromise some or all of its design goals, in which case alternative systems could be considered. Another view is that in a more dynamic environment, that is, one in which the circumstances could vary, *e.g.*, as a function of time of day, traffic loading, or other factors, that could be described on a statistical basis, the system performance goals would be appropriately adjusted.⁶ This would give rise to system concepts, which could be implemented dynamically—on the fly—for example, by software radio.⁷

The existing FCC policies of technical flexibility and competition already permit this enhanced approach that focuses not only on the competitive goal of getting the desired amount of “good bits-per-second” through a licensee’s optimally designed system and to the market, but also on the goal of creating extra communications capability, if possible, and getting that capability to market. Although such an enhanced approach to design that more fully exploits the spectrum resources is already allowed under most existing FCC policies, licensees generally follow the traditional, customary approaches, because the design process is focused on the single goal of delivering communications services to the marketplace. One of the points of this paper is that an additional goal that extracts more capability from the spectrum resource, while not compromising the original competitive goal, may be achievable and that that capability may also be delivered to the marketplace. A more intense use of the spectrum would be the result of such an enhanced approach, which would further a fundamental FCC objective.⁸

While the FCC’s policy of technical flexibility has been in force since the late ‘80s and has continued to be expanded as new bands are opened up, licensees usually use their flexibility to the benefit of the provisioning of their own services, adding additional features, capabilities, and capacities. It is one of the goals of this paper to more

⁶ V. Bose, R Hu, and R. Morris, “Dynamic Physical Layers for Wireless Networks Using Software Radio,” International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, Salt Lake City, UT, May 2001.

⁷ R. Hu, *Controlling Physical Layer Parameters for Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks*. Master’s thesis. Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2001.

⁸ J. Muleta (in collaboration with T. Stanley), “Moore’s Law & What Do We Do When We Get There: Squeezing Moore Out of the Electromagnetic Spectrum.” Proceedings of Wireless Telecommunications Symposium WTS-2004, May 14-15, 2004, Pomona CA, <http://www.csupomona.edu/~wtts/proceedings.htm>.

intensely exploit the spectrum resource by illustrating that flexibility also permits alternative designs that may create additional capabilities that have market value and could be taken to the marketplace. With the addition of new policies for spectrum leasing and secondary market policies, the FCC has taken further steps to encourage licensees to more fully exploit the spectrum to which the licensees have been licensed.

IV. IMPOSITION OF EXTERNAL CONSTRAINT: COMMUNICATIONS TAX

The preceding discussion illustrates the design trade-offs for licensee objectives of getting a desired reliable data rate for system performance in a traditional design or doing so with an additional objective of creating extra communications capability in an enhanced design. Each of these objectives directly benefits the licensee, who presumably would reap the benefit in the marketplace of the expenditure of the resources of bandwidth and power under the terms of the license. Consider another problem in which the licensee would have to design its system, but with an additional and extraneous condition that would be external to the licensee's objectives and hence benefit in the marketplace.

Suppose that as an additional design condition, the noise level to be used in the design were not the customary level, but an arbitrarily higher one. The impact of this condition can be illustrated by examining the operating point in Figure 4. The direct effect would be to move the operating point horizontally to the left, along the line separating Regions D and E, since a higher noise level would mean an E_b/N_o that was smaller than the design-level E_b/N_o . The immediate observation is that such a system would have degraded performance relative to the original design since the P_B would be less than the design-level of P_B and the resulting bit error rate would be higher; that is, this would be a less reliable system.

The licensee has two recourses to follow to regain the original performance objectives. The simplest action to take would be for the licensee to increase the power in the design in order to increase the reduced E_b/N_o back to the design level. This would move the operating point horizontally to the right back to the original location. The original performance would be regained, but at an extra expense of increased power. An alternative action would be to move the operating vertically down to the curve that represents the design-level P_B . This would not move the operating point back to the original location, but it would mean a system design with the desired design-level P_B . However, the value of R/W would be reduced, relative to the design-level R/W . Since the original performance

Figure 4. Extra Resources Needed to Restore Desired Design Goals, If External Constraint Are Imposed

objective was to maintain a desired level of data, that is, R is already fixed, then a smaller R/W means that W must be larger. The original performance would be regained, but at an extra expense of increased bandwidth. In either case, if the licensee does not wish to operate a degraded system, the fact that an increased level of noise was inserted to the design means that the licensee would have to invest additional amounts of power or bandwidth to design the desired system of choice. In effect the licensee has been "taxed" in the sense that the choices are degraded performance or the extra expenditures of power or bandwidth.

No opinion is offered in this paper as to whether the FCC "should" or "should not" impose an external constraint in order to fulfill a regulatory objective. The FCC in fact has the authority to impose such regulations and has done so to promote spectrum sharing. Recent examples are briefly discussed next. The point that is being made is that the imposition of a constraint external to the design of a communications system is not "free," but comes at a cost that is usually paid by the incumbent licensees, *e.g.*, when the FCC decides that a new service or application can share the same spectrum band with an existing service, if the impact on the incumbents is determined to be tolerably small.

Examples of the FCC's imposing external constraints on existing licensees include circumstances where licensed and unlicensed entities are beneficiaries. A licensed terrestrial fixed service has been added to the 500 megahertz band occupied by the Direct Broadcast Satellite community based on specified performance parameters restricting the terrestrial system. The FCC stated that these parameters would ensure that the establishment of the terrestrial service in the same band would lead to less than a 10% increase in DBS signal outage in almost all cases. The FCC's interpretation of no "harmful interference" was

supported by its detailed statistical analysis of signal unavailability in the increased noise environment demonstrating that DBS operations would not be seriously degraded or subject to repeated interruptions and that the increased noise from the terrestrial system as it would affect DBS subscribers would be generally unnoticed. The FCC in effect had decided that the impact of the extra noise in the band, which it had quantified, was sufficiently small so as to be tolerable and hence would not be noticed by DBS subscribers.⁹ Similarly, the FCC has adopted rules to permit Ultra-Wideband devices to be authorized as unlicensed equipment. UWB devices operate over wide swaths of frequencies significantly reducing their radiated power levels into a wide range of communications systems. The FCC's restrictions on power and frequencies of use are intended to protect the receivers of these other systems whose bands the devices overlap.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Sklar, *Digital Communications, Fundamentals and Applications, 2nd*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey 07458, 2001, pp. 521-522.
- [2] C. E. Shannon, "Communication in the Presence of Noise," *Proc. IRE*, **37**, No.1, pp. 10-21, January 1949.
- [3] B. Sklar, "A Structured Overview of Digital Communications—a Tutorial Review—Part 1," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, August 1983.
- [4] B. Sklar, "Defining, Designing, Evaluation Digital Communication Systems," *IEEE Comm. Magazine*, November 1993.

⁹ See Memorandum Opinion and Order and Second Report and Order, 17 F.C.C. Rcd. 9641 (2002), ¶ 68.